

Evaluation of Abu Dhabi University Professional Diploma in Teaching Program according to the Students

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 15, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 19, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Evaluation, Professional Diploma ,Program, Students.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5579295</p>	<p><i>This study aimed at evaluating the professional diploma in teaching program at Abu Dhabi University as viewed by the students. The study used the descriptive analytical approach. The data collection tool used was a questionnaire of 39 items under four parts: program objectives, program contents, program outcomes and the teaching and learning process. Having verified validity and reliability of the tool, the researcher distributed it to the sample of the study which consisted of 271 students who enrolled in the program in 2017/2018. The statistical analysis revealed a number of findings including: the students' evaluation of the program was high across all the parts and there are no statistically significant differences between the evaluations of the four parts neither are there such differences depending on the variables of gender, specialization, years of experience or the educational stage. In light of the findings, the researcher presented some recommendations.</i></p>

Introduction

Educators unanimously agree that the teacher is the cornerstone of the teaching process and assumes the greatest responsibility of achieving its objectives. Therefore, the appropriate preparation of the teacher academically, professionally and culturally has gained high importance. Universities are keen on offering programs that provide educational experiences enabling teachers to keep abreast of latest technological developments, have access to any updates in the field of education and satisfy the changing needs of the community (Ibrahim, 2009). In view of the successive developments in knowledge, culture, education, etc. there are more and more calls to increase the efforts for promoting teacher preparation programs and building the 21st century's teacher who has deep and wide knowledge, updates his/her knowledge according to findings of various research and has excellent professional and academic qualification (Mahmoud, 2004).

2. Study Problem:

The vital role performed by the teacher at the educational process and his/her key role in educating the generations make it highly important for universities to offer teacher preparation programs. Such programs aim at qualifying teachers as professional educators following world-class standards. Abu Dhabi University takes the lead in this field. Because of continuously increasing enrollment in the professional diploma in teaching program, it has become necessary for this program to undergo evaluation. The quality of the program should be assessed by the students enrolled as their opinions are basic elements of the program development and identifying its strengths and weaknesses.

3. Study Questions:

Question 1: What is the level of evaluation of the professional diploma program in teaching at Abu Dhabi University according to the students?

Question 2: : Are there statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the level of evaluation of the professional diploma program in teaching at Abu Dhabi University according to the students in different fields (objectives, content, outputs, learning and education)?

Question 3: Are there statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the level of evaluation of the professional diploma program in teaching at Abu Dhabi University according to the students and in view of the variables of gender, specialization, experience and educational stage?

4. Importance of Study:

The feedback the study will avail regarding the evaluation of the professional diploma program may help Abu Dhabi University as an offeror of the program to take appropriate decisions whether to keep the program at its current status or make some improvements. It also provides the faculty members with complete information about the teaching and learning process included in the program and the students' comments to be taken into consideration. The findings will help other beneficiaries such as the Ministry of Education and private school administrations to have a clear idea about to what extent the program enriches knowledge and the skills of teachers and thus improves student performance.

5. Study Limits:

The study is limited to the students enrolled in the professional diploma in teaching at Abu Dhabi University in the academic year 2017/2018.

6. Procedural terminology:

Evaluation: The degree given by the study subjects regarding each of the questionnaire items.

Professional Diploma Program: One of the programs offered by the College of Arts and Sciences of Abu Dhabi University which aims at graduating qualified teachers.

Professional Diploma Program Students: All the students enrolled in the professional diploma in teaching at Abu Dhabi University in the academic year 2017/2018.

Abu Dhabi University: An academic institution and one of the best private universities in the United Arab Emirates, located in the capital city of Abu Dhabi. It was established in 2003.

7. Previous Studies:

This part includes previous studies that have direct relevance to the current study starting from the most recent.

A study Al Malki (2017) conducted a study to evaluate the general diploma program in education at the College of Education, King Abdulaziz University, from students' point of view. The sample consisted of 82 students. The study had a number of findings indicating a moderate degree of quality. The evaluation of the part of teaching was the highest and that of facilities and equipment came last. There were no differences of statistical significance between the responses attributed to any of the variables of specialization or job title except in the part of program management.

Study Al Logmani (2015) carried out a study aiming at exploring the extent of the realization of total quality standards in the general diploma program in education, Islamic University in Madinah as perceived by students. The sample was 233 students and the findings revealed the realization of the total quality standards by a moderate degree. There were no statistically significant differences attributed to the variable of the type of work. However, there were such differences attributed to the type of the school, the discipline of the study at the university and the period between the graduation from the university and the enrollment in the program.

Study Talitha and others (2013) performed a study under the title "Evaluation of Professional Development Program to Deliver the Subject of Multidisciplinary Science". It aimed at evaluating the professional development program for science teachers to help them use various teaching methods. The sample of the study included 13 Dutch teachers who participated in a 10-week training program. The findings revealed a high satisfaction level regarding the program contents and effectivity in the professional development of the teachers. There were no differences of statistical significance attributed to the variable of experience regarding the program satisfaction.

Study Sweidan (2010) aimed at identifying the quality standards that should be met by the general diploma in education at the Cairo University as derived from the UN Development Program's standards of quality and accreditation. The statistical analysis indicated the realization of the required quality in the field of producing teaching and learning sources, the field of the faculty members and the field of the study curricula.

Study Atiat and Atiat (2010) conducted a study to evaluate the general diploma in education at Al Hussein Bin Talal University from students' point of view. The researchers developed a questionnaire of 39 paragraphs covering the fields of the study. The sample consisted of 121 general diploma in education students. The results of student evaluation of all the parts of the study were moderate. There were no differences of statistical significance attributed to the variables of gender and years of experience. The study recommended revising the program study plans and teaching procedures.

Study Al Dhaher and Al Basoumi (2009) conducted a study to evaluate the effectivity of the postgraduate diploma in learning difficulties at Princess Tharwat College from graduates' point of view. The sample consisted of 100 teachers who graduated the program and currently practicing their career. The researchers used a questionnaire for the study. According to the findings, the postgraduate diploma in learning difficulties received high evaluation in the five parts (basic knowledge concepts, evaluation methods, teaching planning, teaching strategies and communication skills). The program's evaluation was moderate in two parts: professional and ethical practices and teaching technology. There were no statistically significant differences between the teachers' degrees of evaluation attributed to variables of gender, specialization and years of experience before and after enrolment in the postgraduate diploma program.

Study Aypay (2009) aimed at evaluating the program of preparing teachers for their career from the point of view of the graduates in Marmara Region, Turkey. The sample consisted of 228 teachers who answered a questionnaire written for this study. Teachers' responses to the five parts of program design, different learning patterns support, productive classroom configuration, teaching and learning evaluation and professional development of teachers were compared based upon the variables of gender, years of experience, school location, educational stage, classroom and school size, socio-economic status of the school and qualification degree of the teacher. The findings showed differences with statistical significance at the level $\alpha=0.05$ in the responses attributed to the years of experience, classroom size and the socio-economic status of the school.

However, there are no statistically significant differences in the responses attributed to school location, school size, and qualification degree of the teacher or the educational stage.

Study Shatnawi and Oleimant (2008) conducted a study with the title: "Extent to which educational diploma programs achieve educational competences under the knowledge-based economy from the point of view of educational diploma students in the Jordanian universities." The tool of data collection was a questionnaire of 30 paragraphs under four parts. 188 educational diploma students responded to the questionnaire. The findings included: the educational diploma program achievement of the educational competences was high and there were no differences of statistical significance regarding the extent to which educational competences are achieved attributed to the variables of the university and the academic department. The study recommended revising the educational diploma program plans in order to achieve the competences, the necessary skills and knowledge as required by the knowledge-based economy. (3)

Study Eid (2006) aimed at evaluating the educational program for kindergarten teachers at the College of Education, Kuwait University. The sample consisted of 4 faculty members, 3 administrative staff, 10 students enrolled in the program and 30 principals and technical supervisors residing in kindergartens. For purposes of collecting data of the study, the researcher used the methods of document analysis, interviews, observation and questionnaire. According to the findings, the program does not meet the international standards of kindergartens. Therefore, the study recommended revision and improvement of the program in order to comply with the international kindergarten standards.

Study Pettway (Pettway, 2004) carried out a study, "Novice teachers' evaluation of teacher preparation program". It aimed at exploring how newly-graduating teachers evaluate the teacher preparation program at the Teacher Preparation College in Osborne University. The researcher used a questionnaire to collect data. Following the descriptive approach, the study reached a number of findings. The most important was the teachers' satisfaction with the program of preparing them as teachers at Osborne University in Alabama, USA. The reason of satisfaction was the availability of quality standards in the teaching experience provided to them. The subjects of the study identified the following as weaknesses of the program: insufficient use of technological methods in teaching and shortness of practical practice period in the program.

Study Celandia (2004) conducted a study, "Second year teachers' perspectives of the teaching criteria leading to quality preparation of teachers". The study aimed at exploring the opinions of the level 2 teachers at the University of Iowa, USA regarding 8 teaching criteria that are part of the improving teacher preparation program. It also aimed at collecting information about an effective, research-based system designed to enhance teachers' performance and understand administrative supervisors' roles in the lesson design program. The researcher used a questionnaire to collect the study data, which was distributed to all the level 2 teachers. The findings of the study included the following: according to level 2 teachers in the University of Iowa, the teaching criteria are based on research and are good for the profession of teaching; the teacher preparation improvement program enhanced the relationships with the trainers, administrative staff and educational supervisors because there were more opportunities for achieving a common goal and the best elements of the program's success were: clear policies, adequate resources, effective institutions, passion for work and appropriate economic, political and social circumstances. According to the findings, these five elements did not receive proper attention.

Study Tomas and Lodman (2001) carried out a study to evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of the preparation program of teachers who hold BA and MA degrees from Carnegie University. The sample consisted of 434 subjects who held bachelor and master's degrees. The researchers used a questionnaire of four parts (job satisfaction, program quality, skill and expertise and class management methods). The findings revealed that the evaluations of all the graduates were high. There were no differences of statistical significance attributed to the degree level (bachelor or masters). There were differences of statistical significance in the program evaluation attributed to the variable of gender. Female subjects' evaluation of the program was more positive.

Study Trice (2000) conducted a study to evaluate the postgraduate programs at the University of Oxford. The study revealed that 72% of the 928 students were satisfied with the quality of the academic experience they received. 90% of the respondents were satisfied with the competence of the faculty members. 57% of the students provided good evaluation for the teaching quality. 81% of the students indicated that communication with the faculty members was easy. 66% of the students stated that the faculty members support the students and provide them with fruitful feedback.

7.1 Comments of the Previous Study:

Having reviewed the previous studies that are relevant to the present one, the researcher noticed that some studies aimed at addressing the criteria of quality of the teacher preparation programs such as the study of Sweidan (2004). Some studies aimed at evaluating the teacher preparation programs from the graduates' point of view such as the studies of Atiat (2010) and Al Taher and Al Basoumi (2009). Some aimed at evaluating the program from the point of view the program staff including administrative staff and supervisors such as Pettway's study (2004). Therefore, the present study is a continuation of the previous studies as it reflects awareness of the importance of evaluating the educational programs with a view of achieving development and

improving the outcomes of such programs. The previous studies dealt with different parts of evaluation. There were also differences in the results of the evaluations regarding the level of satisfaction. The types of the problems faced by the educational programs were various due to social differences of the subjects of the studies and the differences of the study tool used. The common aspect between this study and the previous ones is that this study aims at evaluating the professional diploma in teaching at Abu Dhabi University from the point of view of the program-enrolled students across various parts and including a number of variables.

8. Study Population and Sample:

The study population is all of the 524 professional diploma in teaching students at Abu Dhabi University in the academic year 2017/2018. The questionnaire was distributed to all students. The researcher managed to collect responses from 271 students; i.e. the sample of the study. Table 1 shows the distribution of the study sample individuals according to the variables.

Table (1): distribution of the sample depending on general information

Variable	Categories	Frequency	percent
Gender	Male	37	13.7
	Female	234	86.3
	Total	271	100.0
Specialization	Arts and Humanities	176	64.9
	Science	95	35.1
	Total	271	100.0
Years of teaching experience	less than 5 years	91	33.6
	5 - 10 years	92	33.9
	11 – 15 years	47	17.3
	more than 15 years	41	15.1
	Total	271	100.0
Stage	KG1 – Grade 5	100	36.9
	Grade 6 – Grade 9	103	38.0
	Grade 10 – Grade 12	68	25.1
	Total	271	100.0

Table (1) shows that:

- For gender variable, the highest percentage reached (86.3%) for (Female), but the lowest percentage reached (13.7%) for (male).
- For specialization variable, the highest percentage reached (64.9%) for (Arts and Humanities), but the lowest percentage reached (35.1%) for (Science).
- For years of teaching experience variable, the highest percentage reached (33.9%) for (5 - 10 years), but the lowest percentage reached (15.1%) for (more than 15 years).
- For stage variable, the highest percentage reached (38%) for (Grade 6 – Grade 9), but the lowest percentage reached (25.1%) for (Grade 10 – Grade 12).

8. Study Tool: The researcher designed the study tool depending on the literature which addressed similar issues. The researcher reviewed a number of studies such as the study of (Al Malki, 2017), the study of (Al Logmani, 2015) and the study of (Al Daaja et al. 2011). Afterwards, the researcher designed the study tool which consisted of 39 paragraphs under four parts: the program objectives – 7 paragraphs; the program content – 9 paragraphs, the program outcomes - 10 paragraphs and the teaching and learning – 13 paragraphs.

9. Reliability Analysis: In order to ensure the reliability (Test R. test) of the tool, it has been applied twice a week with a time lag on the exploratory sample consisting of (40) of Abu Dhabi University students selected from outside the original sample, then Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated between the two applications to extract the reliability by (Test R. test). Also, in order to ensure the reliability of the tool, it has been applied on the original sample. This is shown in table (2).

Table (2): the result of reliability (Cronbach Alpha)

No	Domain	Cronbach Alpha	reliability Test R. test	Item No
1	Program Objectives	0.93	0.92	7
2	Program Content	0.92	0.90	9
3	Program Outcomes	0.96	0.95	10
4	Teaching and Learning	0.93	0.91	13
	Total instrument	0.97	0.96	55

Table (2) shows that:

- The highest Cronbach' alpha value reached (0.96) for "Program Outcomes". And the lowest alpha value was (0.92) for "Program Content". But the total alpha values of "Total instrument" reached (0.97); this indicates achievement of reliability.

- The highest reliability Test R. test value reached (0.95) for "Program Outcomes". And the lowest alpha value was (0.91) for "Teaching and Learning". But the total reliability Test R. test of "Total instrument" reached (0.96); this indicates achievement of reliability Test R. test.

9.1 Scale correction:The final resolution consisted of (39) paragraphs, where the researcher used the Leckert scale for the pentagram to measure the opinions of the members of the study sample, was given strongly agree (5), agree (4), neutral (3), disagree (2), strongly disagree (1), by placing a signal (\surd) in front of the answer their degree of approval, and the following classification has been relied upon to determine the arithmetic averages as follows:

- Less than 2.5 is low
- From 2.5-3.5 is medium
- More than 3.5 is high

10.The result and discussion:

This part presents findings of study which aims to know Evaluation of Abu Dhabi University Professional Diploma in Teaching Program according to the Students. It also includes answers of the questions.

The first question: What is the level of evaluation of the professional diploma program in teaching at Abu Dhabi University according to the students?

To answer this question, means and standard deviation for each domain and for each item of each domain items, and grand mean of them were extracted; tables below show that.

Table (3): Means and standard deviation for each domain and grand mean of "evaluation of the professional diploma program in teaching" (n= 271)

No	Domain	Mean	Standard. Deviation	Rank	Agreement Degree
1	Program Objectives	3.79	0.82	3	High
2	Program Content	3.77	0.76	4	High
3	Program Outcomes	3.88	0.85	2	High
4	Teaching and Learning	4.06	0.69	1	High
	Grand Mean	3.90	0.69	-	High

Table (3) shows that the highest means reached (4.06) out of (5) for domain (4) "Teaching and Learning" by high agreement degree, then for domain (3) "Program Outcomes" (mean 3.88) by high agreement degree, then for domain (1) "Program Objectives" (mean 3.79) by high agreement degree. And the lowest mean was (3.77) for domain (2) "Program Content" by high agreement degree.

The grand mean for "evaluation of the professional diploma program in teaching" reached (3.90) with a high agreement degree.

- Table (4) shows the means and standard deviation for "Program Objectives". It finally shows the grand mean.

Table (4): Means and standard deviation for items and grand mean "Program Objectives"

No	Domain	Mean	Standard. Deviation	Rank	Agreement Degree
1	Program objectives meet teachers' educational needs	3.94	0.89	1	Medium
2	Program objectives are suitable for the latest developments of the educational process	3.86	0.95	3	Medium
3	The program has clear objectives that it is designed to achieve	3.92	0.91	2	Medium
4	Program objectives are different from those of the school where I work	3.70	0.99	6	Low
5	Program objectives are strongly linked to the practical side of teaching	3.85	0.99	4	Medium
6	Program objectives can be measured and evaluated	3.81	0.96	5	Medium
7	Program objectives are part of the incentives for my enrollment in the program	3.42	1.19	7	Medium
	Grand mean	3.79	0.82	-	Medium

Table (4) shows that the highest means reached (3.94) out of (5) for item (1) "Program objectives meet teachers' educational needs" by high agreement degree, then for item (3) "The program has clear objectives that it is designed to achieve" (means 3.92) by high agreement degree, then for item (2) "Program objectives are suitable for the latest developments of the educational process" (means 3.86) by high agreement degree, and the lowest

means was (3.42) for item (7) "Program objectives are part of the incentives for my enrollment in the program" by medium agreement degree. The grand mean "Program Objectives" reached (3.79) by high agreement degree.

- Means and standard deviation for "Program Content" item and grand mean of them, table (5) shows that.

Table (5): Means and standard deviation for items and grand mean "Program Content"

No	Domain	Mean	Standard. Deviation	Rank	Agreement Degree
1	The courses of the program meet teachers' educational needs	3.85	0.95	1	High
2	Educational competencies of the program are adequate to develop teachers' abilities and skills	3.74	0.95	8	High
3	The various courses of the program address contemporary educational issues	3.81	0.97	3	High
4	The program content is characterized by intellectual enrichment and accuracy	3.75	0.94	6	High
5	The textbooks of the study plan are interlaced	3.75	0.97	6	High
6	The contents of the courses can achieve the program objectives	3.76	0.91	5	High
7	The sources of information related to the contents of the courses are characterized by diversity	3.82	0.90	2	High
8	The program study plan is suitable for the time allocated to it	3.71	1.01	9	High
9	The content of textbooks has updated and accurate information	3.78	1.04	4	High
Grand mean		3.77	0.76	-	High

Table (5) shows that the highest means reached (3.85) out of (5) for item (1) "The courses of the program meet teachers' educational needs" by high agreement degree, then for item (7) "The sources of information related to the contents of the courses are characterized by diversity" (means 3.82) by high agreement degree, then for item (3) "The various courses of the program address contemporary educational issues" (means 3.81) by high agreement degree, and the lowest means was (3.71) for item (8) "The program study plan is suitable for the time allocated to it" by high agreement degree. The grand mean "Program Content" reached (3.77) by high agreement degree.

- Means and standard deviation for "Program Outcomes" item and grand mean of them, table (6) shows that.

Table (6): Means and standard deviation for items and grand mean "Program Outcomes"

No	Domain	Mean	Standard. Deviation	Rank	Agreement Degree
1	The program provides me with various experiences and skills useful for my career	4.04	0.89	1	High
2	The program enhances teachers' self-confidence and job satisfaction	3.92	0.96	2	High
3	The Program considers the teacher as someone who steers and organizes the educational process rather than someone practicing spoon-feeding.	3.91	0.98	4	High
4	The program, as a career qualification one, links theory to practice.	3.68	1.05	10	High
5	The program provides me with modern classroom management skills.	3.90	0.96	5	High
6	The program helps teachers to identify their own strengths to promote and weaknesses to avoid.	3.84	0.96	9	High
7	The program provides me with modern teaching methods and strategies	3.92	1.02	2	High
8	The program helps me to use evaluation methods that are more effective to measure students' achievement.	3.85	1.03	7	High
9	The program provides me with the skills of dealing with different categories of special education students.	3.85	1.02	7	High

10	The program provides me with modern educational technological applications.	3.88	1.01	6	High
Grand mean		3.88	0.85	-	High

Table (6) shows that the highest means reached (4.04) out of (5) for item (1) "The program provides me with various experiences and skills useful for my career" by high agreement degree, then for item (2) "The program enhances teachers' self-confidence and job satisfaction" and item (7) "The program provides me with modern teaching methods and strategies" (means 3.92) by high agreement degree, and the lowest means was (3.68) for item (4) "The program, as a career qualification one, links theory to practice" by high agreement degree. The grand mean "Program Outcomes" reached (3.88) by high agreement degree.

- Means and standard deviation for "Teaching and Learning" item and grand mean of them, table (8) shows that.

Table (8): Means and standard deviation for items and grand mean "Teaching and Learning"

No	Domain	Mean	Standard. Deviation	Rank	Agreement Degree
1	The program courses are taught by competent faculty members	4.20	0.84	4	High
2	Student attendance is checked regularly	4.32	0.87	2	High
3	There is compliance with lectures' start and end times.	4.36	0.79	1	High
4	Modern technologies are used in the learning process	4.06	1.01	8	High
5	Diversified teaching methods enhancing creativity and strengthening motivation are used	3.79	1.10	12	High
6	Faculty members take into consideration age differences between students	3.64	1.17	13	Medium
7	Students' practical experiences are activated in order to enrich the contents and activities of different courses	3.96	0.99	10	High
8	Teaching materials are uploaded to the Blackboard in due course.	4.26	0.84	3	High
9	Evaluation methods cover all contents of the textbook.	4.10	0.90	7	High
10	Evaluation methods that are used take into consideration student individual differences	3.81	1.04	11	High
11	Methods of course evaluation are announced to students at the beginning of the semester.	4.14	0.82	5	High
12	Evaluation methods are diversified according to theoretical and practical aspects.	3.97	0.93	9	High
13	There is an emphasis on the integrity of students' coursework.	4.13	0.82	6	High
Grand mean		4.06	0.69	-	High

Table (8) shows that the highest means reached (4.36) out of (5) for item (3) "There is compliance with lectures' start and end times" by high agreement degree, then for item (2) "Student attendance is checked regularly" (means 4.32) by high agreement degree, then for item (8) "Teaching materials are uploaded to the Blackboard in due course" (means 4.26) by high agreement degree, and the lowest means was (3.68) for item (6) "Faculty members take into consideration age differences between students" by high agreement degree. The grand mean "Teaching and Learning" reached (4.06) by high agreement degree.

According to the results related to the first question, the students' evaluation of the program was high across all levels. The researcher attributes this result to the fact that the program has been offered in Abu Dhabi University since 8 years and has gone through development and improvement stages rendering it an excellent program able to satisfy the different needs of teachers. It complies with the mission of Abu Dhabi University to deliver quality education through all of its programs.

As regards the points receiving low evaluation, regardless of the general average, the fourth point on the objectives indicated differences between the objectives of the program and those of schools. The researcher believes that such differences result from the international standards of the program, which are not followed by some schools. The sixth point, which also revealed low evaluation, was relevant to teaching and learning. It addressed the issue of teachers' consideration of age differences of the students. The researcher attributes this low evaluation to the fact that the faculty members observe justice and equality in all assignments and coursework assigned to students in order to avoid any partiality in favor of a certain group over another.

The second question: Are there statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the level of evaluation of the professional diploma program in teaching at Abu Dhabi University according to the students in different fields (objectives, content, outputs, learning and education)?

To answer this question, means and standard deviation for study domains (Program Objectives, Program Content, Program Outcomes, Teaching and Learning) were computed depending on table (3) and one Way ANOVA was applied, table (9) shows that.

Table (9) results of one Way ANOVA to explore differences in fields (objectives, content, outputs, learning and education).

Source	Sum of square	Degree freedom	Mean square	F. value	Sig.
Between Groups	13.875	3	4.625	7.577	.000
Within Groups	659.239	1080	.610		
Total	673.114	1083			

Table (9) shows that there is significant differences at the level of ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the level of evaluation of the professional diploma program in teaching at Abu Dhabi University according to the students in different fields (objectives, content, outputs, learning and education), whereas (F. value) was (7.577) by significant level (0.00), the post hoc test "scheffe" results shows that these differences to favor of (Teaching and Learning) by means (4.06) but other domains means less than.

Table (10) results of "Scheffe" test for domains

Domains	N	Subset for alpha = .05	
		1	2
Program Content	271	3.7741	
Program Objectives	271	3.7881	
Program Outcomes	271	3.8779	3.8779
Teaching and Learning	271		4.0579
Sig.		.496	.047

Means for groups in homogeneous subsets are displayed.

A Uses Harmonic Mean Sample Size = 271.0.

The researcher explains that this finding results from the holistic approach the University follows while dealing with the program. The program objectives, contents, outcomes and the teaching and learning process are developed and improved every year according to the feedback received from students and faculty members.

The third question: Are there statistically significant differences at the level of ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the level of evaluation of the professional diploma program in teaching at Abu Dhabi University according to the students according to the variables (gender, specialization, experience and teaching level)?

To answer this question, means and standard deviation for study domains (Program Objectives, Program Content, Program Outcomes, Teaching and Learning) and total instrument were extracted due to (gender, specialization, experience and teaching level). To explore differences in total instrument the (4- Way ANOVA) was applied, and explore differences in domains the (MANOVA) was applied to, tables below show that.

Table (11): means and standard deviation of domains and total instrument due to (gender, specialization, experience and teaching level)

Domain	Variable	Categories	Means	Standard. Deviation
Program Objectives	Gender	Male	3.95	0.76
		Female	3.76	0.83
	Specialization	Arts and Humanities	3.80	0.87
		Science	3.76	0.72
	Years of teaching experience	less than 5 years	3.87	0.68
		5 - 10 years	3.79	0.87
		11 – 15 years	3.71	0.90
		more than 15 years	3.68	0.88
	Stage	KG1 – Grade 5	3.88	0.79
Grade 6 – Grade 9		3.70	0.90	
Grade 10 – Grade 12		3.78	0.73	
Program Content	Gender	Male	3.85	0.82
		Female	3.76	0.75
	Specialization	Arts and Humanities	3.77	0.77
		Science	3.78	0.73

	Years of teaching experience	less than 5 years	3.80	0.67
		5 - 10 years	3.82	0.78
		11 – 15 years	3.62	0.82
		more than 15 years	3.78	0.82
	Stage	KG1 – Grade 5	3.84	0.71
		Grade 6 – Grade 9	3.72	0.82
Grade 10 – Grade 12		3.76	0.73	
Program Outcomes	Gender	Male	3.92	0.92
		Female	3.87	0.84
	Specialization	Arts and Humanities	3.86	0.90
		Science	3.90	0.74
	Years of teaching experience	less than 5 years	4.01	0.65
		5 - 10 years	3.93	0.87
		11 – 15 years	3.76	0.98
		more than 15 years	3.60	0.95
	Stage	KG1 – Grade 5	4.01	0.75
		Grade 6 – Grade 9	3.79	0.96
		Grade 10 – Grade 12	3.82	0.79
	Teaching and Learning	Gender	Male	4.17
Female			4.04	0.69
Specialization		Arts and Humanities	4.08	0.69
		Science	4.02	0.71
Years of teaching experience		less than 5 years	4.09	0.60
		5 - 10 years	4.10	0.73
		11 – 15 years	3.95	0.77
		more than 15 years	4.03	0.73
Stage		KG1 – Grade 5	4.12	0.65
		Grade 6 – Grade 9	3.99	0.75
		Grade 10 – Grade 12	4.06	0.67
Total instrument		Gender	Male	3.99
	Female		3.88	0.68
	Specialization	Arts and Humanities	3.90	0.70
		Science	3.89	0.66
	Years of teaching experience	less than 5 years	3.96	0.57
		5 - 10 years	3.94	0.72
		11 – 15 years	3.78	0.79
		more than 15 years	3.80	0.73
	Stage	KG1 – Grade 5	3.99	0.64
		Grade 6 – Grade 9	3.82	0.75
		Grade 10 – Grade 12	3.88	0.64

Table (11) shows that virtual differences between means of study domains (Program Objectives, Program Content, Program Outcomes, Teaching and Learning) and total instrument due to (gender, specialization, experience and teaching level) variables, therefore (MANOVA) was applied, table (12) shows that

Table (12): the results of (MANOVA) to explore the difference in study domains due to (gender, specialization, experience and teaching level)

Variable	domain	Sum of square	Df	M.S	"F" value	Sig
Gender Hotelling (0.017) F (1.118) Sig (0.348)	Program Objectives	2.233	1	2.233	3.340	0.069
	Program Content	0.729	1	0.729	1.261	0.263
	Program Outcomes	0.883	1	0.883	1.251	0.264
	Teaching and Learning	1.111	1	1.111	2.299	0.131
Specialization Hotelling (0.010) F (0.634) Sig (0.939)	Program Objectives	0.074	1	0.074	0.111	0.739
	Program Content	0.074	1	0.074	0.127	0.722
	Program Outcomes	0.039	1	0.039	0.056	0.813
	Teaching and Learning	0.157	1	0.157	0.326	0.569
Experience Wilk's (0.934) F (1.490) Sig (0.123)	Program Objectives	1.543	3	0.514	0.769	0.512
	Program Content	1.477	3	0.492	0.851	0.467
	Program Outcomes	4.229	3	1.410	1.999	0.115
	Teaching and Learning	1.040	3	0.347	0.717	0.543

Level Wilk's (0.986) F (0.470) Sig (0.877)	Program Objectives	1.731	2	0.865	1.294	0.276
	Program Content	0.949	2	0.474	0.820	0.441
	Program Outcomes	1.860	2	.930	1.318	0.269
	Teaching and Learning	0.990	2	0.495	1.024	0.361
Error	Program Objectives	175.836	263	0.669		
	Program Content	152.130	263	0.578		
	Program Outcomes	185.487	263	0.705		
	Teaching and Learning	127.124	263	0.483		
Corrected total	Program Objectives	180.891	270			
	Program Content	154.922	270			
	Program Outcomes	193.387	270			
	Teaching and Learning	130.038	270			

* Statistically significant at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$)

Table (12) shows that:

- There are NO a statistic significant differences in study domains (Program Objectives, Program Content, Program Outcomes, Teaching and Learning) due to (gender, specialization, experience and teaching level), where F values do not reach at a statistic significant level.

Table (13): the results of (4- Way ANOVA) to explore the difference in total instrument due to (gender, specialization, experience and teaching level)

Variable	Sum of square	D.F	M.S	"F" value	Sig
Gender	1.118	1	1.118	2.379	0.124
Specialization	0.005	1	0.005	0.010	0.921
Experience	1.498	3	0.499	1.062	0.366
Teaching level	1.279	2	0.639	1.360	0.258
Error	123.658	263	0.470		
Corrected total	127.308	270			

Table (13) shows:

- There are NO a statistic significant difference in total instrument due to (gender, specialization, experience and teaching level), where F values do not reach at a statistic significant level.

The researcher attributes the inexistence of statistically significant differences of the diploma in teaching program evaluations from students' points of views attributed to the variables of gender, specialization, years of experience and educational stage to the fact that the program is designed to be suitable all groups: male and female, experienced or newly-appointed and regardless of the educational stage the teacher teaches or the teacher's specialization.

11. Recommendations:

In the light of the results of this study, the researcher recommends the following:

- 1- Reviewing the objectives and contents of the program from time to time to keep abreast of any developments in the educational field.
- 2- Relying on faculty members under permanent employment to teach the courses of the program to maintain its objectives, outcomes and content.
- 3- Conducting training courses for faculty members to focus on some of the things that students have asked, such as taking into consideration the age differences between students and the diversity of evaluation methods.....
- 4- Conducting other studies showing the practical application of theoretical subjects taught by students.

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